

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Tourism software platform with intersections with social media and recommendation systems

SPOKE N 3 – Tourism and culture industry

FP TOEP - TOURISM OPEN-ENDED EXPERIMENTATION PLATFORM

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Version history

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Glossary

Definition	
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.

Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

1. TOEP - Tourism Open-ended Experimentation Platform

TOEP is a multi-interface platform designed to connect regional activity providers with residents and tourists (see Figure 1). The platform features distinct user interfaces tailored for both providers and users. Providers are enabled to add and manage regional activities. Users can browse, register for, and provide feedback on these activities. The following report will detail the development process of TOEP, including the architectural design, developed functions, and the recommendation system.

Figure 1. TOEP web page for Providers activity management and end-user app home.

2. Overall Architecture

The TOEP system architecture (see Figure 2) is based on two distinct interfaces, each designed for a different user type. Both interfaces connect to a centralized database that stores all information related to activities created by tourism providers, as well as the profiles of users (potential participants in these activities). Utilizing this data, a recommendation system filters activities that best match the user's profile and geographic location, thereby suggesting relevant and localized experiences.

Figure 2. TOEP overall architecture.

TOEP utilizes a robust tech stack: a web interface for providers and a mobile app for users. The apps are built using Ionic Framework and Angular for cross-platform development and efficient user interaction. Both integrate with a scalable cloud-based MongoDB database and a Node.js API for efficient server-side operations. The server-side components run on a virtual machine hosted on the Chameleon Project, a cloud computing testbed supported by the National Science Foundation. Additionally, Firebase is used for user authentication. These technologies enable efficient handling of user requests, intuitive user interface design, and reliable communication with the database. At the core of TOEP's personalization is its Recommendation System. This system is powered by machine learning algorithms that analyze user data to generate highly personalized activity recommendations, enhancing the user experience.

3. Users and functionalities

The two primary TOEP clients are Users and Providers. The Users group employs the platform to discover activities that align with their individual profiles, factoring in interests, current location, and recommendations influenced by similar users. Users may include tourists, travelers, residents, and more. Users have a mobile app that allows them to perform different activities:

- **Profile Creation:** complete a detailed profile to improve the accuracy of recommendations, save their activity category preferences and add their favorite activities to a list (Figure 3.a).
- **Personalized Search:** conduct a Map-based activity search based on their interests, location, and other criteria (Figure 3.b).
- **Intelligent Recommendations:** receive personalized activity suggestions thanks to a recommendation system that analyzes their preferences and the behavior of similar users (Figure 3.b).
- **Online Bookings:** make reservations directly from the app and receive instant confirmations (Figure 3.c).
- **Ratings:** Rate and leave comments on completed activities, contributing to the improvement of the information available on the platform (Figure 3.d).

a)

b)

c)

d)

Figure 3. TOEP user interface examples.

Conversely, Provider entities utilize the platform to disseminate, advertise, and assess their tourism initiatives. Providers can encompass enterprises, associations, public agencies, accommodation facilities, and private operators. Providers have a web-based portal that allows them to:

- **Activity management:** create, edit, delete, and publish new tourism activities (Figure 4.a, b and c).
- **Customization:** configure details such as schedules, prices, detailed descriptions, and attach images or videos (Figure 4.c).
- **Performance data:** access information on the performance of their activities, including bookings, reviews, and user ratings (Figure 4.d).

Figure 4. TOEP provider interface example.

Activity Categorization

The platform's data collection process is designed for flexibility and adaptability, accommodating the diverse range of activities offered by providers. The specific information required for each activity is dynamically adapted based on its category (e.g., art, towns, food, nature, shows, traditions, etc.) and type (activity, event or itinerary.). A key differentiator among these types is temporality. For instance, an Event necessitates specific start and end dates and times, as its nature is inherently time-bound. In contrast, an Attraction (like a museum) or a Destination (like a city park) requires information such as operating hours, seasonal availability, and general accessibility, rather than precise beginning and end times. This tailored approach ensures all necessary data is captured efficiently, optimizing both the user's search experience and the provider's ability to effectively showcase their offerings.

Enhanced User Experience: Categorized Suggestions

To further enhance the user experience, the mobile application categorizes activity suggestions into three main groups, as illustrated in Figure 3.a. This intuitive categorization scheme empowers users to quickly identify activities that align with their specific interests and needs, streamlining the discovery process. In particular, the categories for the activity suggestions are:

- *Inspired* activities are closely aligned with a user's individual preferences, providing highly personalized recommendations.
- *Near You* suggestions prioritize activities located in proximity to the user's current location.
- *Highlighted* activities represent the platform's top-rated and most popular options.
- *Recent* activities show those activities that were created recently. They may be outside the user's profile.

The user profile (Figure 3.c) page allows users to adjust their preferences at any time. Here, users can modify their preferences, view a list of favorites activities, and access a history of their past participation, complete with review options.

4. Recommendation System

To improve the user experience, the TOEP platform is provided with a flexible recommendation engine (see Figure 2. Recommendation System). The recommender system reads data from the MongoDB repository and provides two different classical recommendation strategies:

- **Collaborative Filtering (CF)** [1]: the idea is to make predictions (filtering) about the interests of a user by collecting preferences or interest information from many users (collaborating); the underlying assumption is that if two users have agreed on certain items in the past, they are likely to agree on other items in the future.
- **Content-Based (CB)** [2]: this approach suggests items to a user based on the characteristics of the items and a profile of the user's preferences; the core idea is to recommend items that are similar in content to items the user has liked in the past, by matching the attributes of the item profiles with the user's profile (to find new items that the user might like).

The recommender system application is designed to run daily, ensuring that recommendations are consistently updated with any new user interactions or activities. The application is deployed within a Docker container and is executed by a cron job set to run at 00:01 Central European Time (CET). This timing was chosen specifically because the platform is focused on the Piedmont region of Italy, and it is assumed that user traffic will be minimal at midnight, allowing the server to dedicate resources to the recommendation engine without impacting client-side performance.

Synthetic Data Generation using Gemini

The tourism platform, still in its development phase, faced a significant cold-start problem due to the lack of real-world user and activity data. To overcome this, a synthetic dataset was generated using the Gemini 1.5 Flash API. This process involved creating a set of fictitious users, activities, and user reviews, which served as the foundational data for building and evaluating the recommendation system.

To generate the initial set of activities and users, the script uses a repetitive prompting strategy.

It starts with a base prompt that defines the persona of the model, the data to be generated, and the specific output format (a list of JSON objects). The prompt also includes a sample object to ensure strict adherence to the required schema. For reference, Table 1 shows an example of the prompt used to generate users.

Table 1. Prompt for users' generation.

Prompt for users' generation

<p><i>You are in charge of generating data for a tourism website, where users can review the activities they have participated in, your goal is to populate the mongodb database of this website. Let's start to generate users only, they must be resident in the Piedmont region in Italy.</i></p> <p><i>You must use the italian language and you must answer with a list of JSON objects, it is important that the generated list and each object inside it will be perfectly compliant to the JSON standard.</i></p> <p><i>There must be a variety of users, some with preferences for food, some for art, some for shows and some for sports, or a combination of those. Users preferences must be a list of strings with a random combination of values fetched from the following list: {categories}</i></p>	<p><i>You must not generate duplicate users. You must generate exactly 10 users.</i></p> <p><i>Here is an example of an user:</i></p> <pre>{ "id": "C73dff810c27eaCaaC2Cdf0e", "email": "giovanni.rossi@gmail.com", "name": "Giovanni Rossi", "username": "Giovanni", "location": {"lat": 45.450001, "lng": 8.C1CCC7}, "locationName": "Novaro, NO", "phone": "34012345C7", "type": "user", "birthday": 72584C400000, "gender": "male", "preferences": ["food", "art"], }</pre> <p><i>Generated data: ""</i></p>
--	--

Note that **{categories}** is a placeholder to be substituted with the actual available preferences, fetched from the appropriate table in MongoDB. Both the activities prompt and users prompt define the rules for generating data relevant to the Piedmont region of Italy, ensuring a variety of user preferences and unique IDs for each entry. The script then iteratively calls the Gemini API to generate more data, dynamically updating the prompt with the already-generated users and activities to prevent duplicates.

Reviews generation is handled by a function that creates a dynamic prompt for each user. This function embeds the user's preferences and the full list of activities into the prompt, instructing the model to generate a specific number of reviews for that user. This personalized approach ensures that the content of the reviews aligns with the user's defined preferences and that a variety of review scores and text lengths are generated, simulating authentic user behavior.

The prompt for review generation is presented in Table 2. The following placeholders can be noted in this prompt: **{activities}**: this is the list of all the activities previously generated, represented as JSON Objects.

- **{user}**: the user to impersonate as JSON Object.
- **{num_reviews}**: this is an integer that controls the number of reviews to generate; in order to simulate a normal website this number is randomly selected from a normal distribution.

Table 2. Prompt for review generation.

Prompt for review generation

You are in charge of generating data for a tourism website where users can review the activities they have participated in, our goal is to populate the mongodb database of this website. You must use the italian language and you must answer with a list of JSON objects, it is important that the generated list will be perfectly compliant to the JSON standard. You already generated users and activities for this website, now you must generate reviews for the activities.

Considering that you have already generated these activities: {activities}. You now have to generate {num_reviews} reviews for these activities as if you were the following user: {nuser}.

You will generate exactly {num_reviews} reviews for this user. User preferences indicate which categories of activities the user is interested in, so the reviews must be mostly related to those categories, remember that the task is to perfectly mime how a normal user would behave on a normal tourism website.

Some reviews will be more positive, some more negative, some will be neutral, and some will be very detailed, while others will be very short. Remember, variety is key.

It is important that the activityId field is correctly filled in each review and it must refer to actually existing activities, you can fetch them from the list I gave you above.

Here is an example of an user:

```
{  
  "id": "78Sghg810c27ghCaaC2Cff08",  
  "userId": user[ "id"],  
  "activityId": "S73gfg811f2SgeCab727hf0S",  
  "mainScore": 4,  
  "staffScore": 5,  
  "text": "Bellissima esperienza, lo staff `e stato molto cordiale e la location ci ha stupito!",  
  "editTimestamp": 1727345204000  
}
```

Generated data: ""

Content-Based Recommender

The Content-Based Recommender is designed to suggest activities to a user based on the textual content of activities they have previously reviewed. The process involves vectorizing activity descriptions, building a user profile, and performing a similarity search. We implemented two different vectorization techniques:

- **Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF)** based: activities are vectorized by means of their description's TF-IDF representation.
- **Semantic based**: activities are vectorized by embedding their description in a dense vector using the Jina sentence embedding model [3].

The core of this system relies on the TF-IDF technique to represent each activity's description as a vector [4]. The process can be formalized as follows:

1. First each activity a_j is represented as its TF-IDF vector $v_{a_j} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ where d is the size of the vocabulary. The TF-IDF score for a term t_k in an activity description a_j is given by:

$$\text{TF-IDF}(t_k, a_j) = \text{TF}(t_k, a_j) \cdot \text{IDF}(t_k)$$

Where $\text{TF}(t_k, a_j)$ is the term frequency of t_k in a_j and $\text{IDF}(t_k)$ is the inverse document frequency of t_k across all activity descriptions.

2. A user's profile, u_i , is constructed as a centroid vector. This vector is the weighted mean of the TF-IDF vectors of all activities, A_i , that user i has reviewed. The weights, $r_{i,j}$, correspond to the user's review score for activity $j \in A_i$. The centroid is defined as:

$$u_i = \frac{\sum_{j \in A_i} r_{i,j} \cdot v_{a_j}}{\sum_{j \in A_i} r_{i,j}}$$

3. Recommendations for a user i are generated by calculating the cosine similarity between their profile vector, u_i , and the TF-IDF vectors of all activities a_k that they have not yet reviewed. The set of unreviewed activities is denoted

as A_i .

$$\text{similarity}(u_i, v_{a_k}) = \frac{u_i \cdot v_{a_k}}{\|u_i\| \|v_{a_k}\|}$$

4. The final recommendations $\mathcal{L}_{i,N}$ for user i are obtained by ranking all activities in A_i in descending order based on their cosine similarity scores. The top N activities from this ranked list are then selected and presented to the user.

The semantic recommender leverages dense vector embeddings to capture the underlying meaning of activity descriptions rather than relying solely on surface-level word statistics. In this approach, each activity description is transformed into a dense numerical representation using the Jina Embeddings model. These embeddings map semantically similar descriptions closer together in the vector space, even if they do not share exact terms. The process can be formalized as follows:

1. First each activity a_j is converted into its embedding vector $v_{a_j} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ where m is the embedding dimension of the pretrained Jina model.
2. The user profile u_i is constructed as the weighted centroid of embeddings of all activities previously reviewed by the user. The same weighting scheme as in the TF-IDF recommender is applied, using the user's review score $r_{i,j}$:

$$u_i = \frac{\sum_{j \in A_i} r_{i,j} \cdot v_{a_j}}{\sum_{j \in A_i} r_{i,j}}$$

3. For generating recommendations, the cosine similarity between the user profile u_i and the embedding vectors of unseen activities v_{a_k} , with $a_k \in A_i$, is computed:

$$\text{similarity}(u_i, v_{a_k}) = \frac{u_i \cdot v_{a_k}}{\|u_i\| \|v_{a_k}\|}$$

4. The list of recommendations $\mathcal{L}_{i,N}$ then consists of the top N activities ranked by similarity score, with higher values indicating greater semantic alignment with the user's interests.

The Collaborative Filtering recommender leverages the collective behavior of users to identify and suggest activities. This system is built upon a matrix factorization approach. The process can be formalized as follows:

1. The foundation is a user-item interaction matrix, $\mathcal{R} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, where m is the number of users and n is the number of activities. Each entry \mathcal{R}_{ij} represents the review score given by user i for activity j , with $\mathcal{R}_{ij} = 0$ if user i has not reviewed activity j .
2. The similarity between any two users i and j is measured using the cosine distance between their rating vectors, r_i and r_j :

$$\text{similarity}(i, j) = \cos(\theta) = \frac{r_i \cdot r_j}{\|r_i\| \|r_j\|}$$

3. For a given user i and an unrated activity j , the predicted rating, \mathcal{R}_{ij} , is calculated as the weighted average of the ratings from a set of k similar users, S_i , who have rated activity j . The weights are the similarity scores between user i and each similar user $s \in S_i$.

Figure 5 shows a graphical depiction of both methods.

Figure 5. Graphical visualization of both recommendation processes.

5. App Validation

We made two validations to TOEP: a heuristic validation to assess the system's underlying logic and user design principles; and a performance validation of the recommender system using quantitative metrics.

User Satisfaction

We employed a heuristic validation methodology to assess the TOEP application. This involved experts critically examining the app to determine its strengths and weaknesses. We specifically adapted parts of different heuristics that measures *perceived usefulness*, *user satisfaction*, *overall reactions*, and *system capabilities*. For the TOEP validation, we incorporated relevant sections from established questionnaires like USE (Usefulness, Satisfaction, and Ease of use) and QUIS (Questionnaire for User Interface Satisfaction). A comprehensive list of questions presented to the expert panel can be found in Table 3.

Table 3. Satisfaction Survey Questions.

SURVEY DIVISION	QUESTIONS
Overall System Satisfaction	Q1 - It helps me be more productive Q2 - It helps me be more effective Q3 - It is useful Q4 - It does everything I would expect it to do Q5 - Is it easy to use
Overall Experience Feeling	Q6 - Terrible ... Wonderful Q7 - Difficult ... Easy Q8 - Frustrating ... Satisfying Q9 - Dull ... Stimulating Q10 - Rigid ... Flexible Q11 - Inadequate power ... Adequate power
Screen Factors	Q12 - Reading characters on the screen Q13 - Organization of information Q14 - Sequence of screens
Terminology And System Feedback	Q15 - Use of terms throughout system Q16 - Terminology related to task Q17 - Position of messages on screen Q18 - Prompts for input Q19 - Error messages
Learning	Q20 - Learning to operate the system Q21 - Performing tasks is straightforward
System Capabilities	Q22 - System speed Q23 - System reliability Q24 - Correcting errors in data entry has been (Difficult ... Easy) Q25 - System tends to be (noisy ... quiet) Q26 - Designed for all levels of users

The validation involved a panel of seven experts: six tourism consultants operating within the European area and one web designer. Their ages ranged from 35 to 47 years, comprising four women and three men. It is important to note that these participants were engaged with the project as content creators, responsible for generating event information, rather than being part of the development team. Consequently, their interaction with the application was limited exclusively to the validation phase.

The participants' initial reactions to their interaction with the application are presented in Figure 6. Based on these results, participants consistently reported above-average scores. The highest values were observed for the app's ease of use (Q5), while the lowest pertained to whether the app met their expectations (Q4). Overall, the application generated modest impact on the participant group.

Overall System Satisfaction

Figure C. Overall system satisfaction results.

Figure 7 presents the results from the more specific aspects of the satisfaction survey. As illustrated in the graphs, the average response per question remained consistent across all inquiries, ranging from 5.67 to 6.67 (on a maximum scale of 9.0). Notably, the highest score was for the perceived organization of information on the screen (Q20), indicating effective information structuring. Conversely, the lowest score pertained to the perceived usefulness of error-support messages. It is important to highlight that participants generally reported no significant issues when using the application, with all scores at least one point above the mean.

A limitation of this validation was that participants interacted with the application exclusively as Providers, thereby restricting their evaluation to the event administration interface. The User-facing functionalities were not assessed given the absence of a real event database; all events for this initial version were AI-generated. This factor may have influenced participants' perception of the application's overall utility and the usability efforts invested in recommending events based on user profiles.

Figure 7. Specific aspects of the satisfaction survey

Recommendation System Performance

The effectiveness of the recommendation algorithms has been verified using four rank-based evaluation metrics: AP@K (Average Precision) [5], NDCG@K (Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain) [6], ERR@K (Expected Reciprocal Rank) [7], and HITS@K (Hit Ratio). Each metric was computed at several values of K, evaluating how well each algorithm ranks relevant activities for the user. All experiments have been performed on the recommendations generated from the synthetic data of users, activities and reviews. The recommendation performance for the three methods: collaborative filtering, TF-IDF, and semantic embedding is illustrated in the Figure 8. Below is a summary of findings for each metric:

- AP@K: the TF-IDF recommender consistently achieves the highest AP@K across all values of K, followed by the semantic and

collaborative filtering approaches, respectively. Both content-based methods outperform collaborative filtering at most cutoffs, and the semantic method shows only slightly lower AP@K than TF-IDF.

- NDCG@K: the TF-IDF recommender again leads, especially at higher ranks. However, both TF-IDF and semantic methods show increasing NDCG@K as K increases, suggesting both provide relevant recommendations deeply into the list. Collaborative filtering achieves similar performance to semantic at higher values of K.
- ERR@K and HITS@K: for ERR@K, TF-IDF matches or slightly outperforms others, with semantic search remaining solidly competitive. HITS@K approaches 1 for all recommenders at higher K, indicating very high recall.

Figure 8. Evaluation of the recommendation algorithms implemented by the Recommendation System.

The results highlight that while TF-IDF is slightly superior across most metrics, the semantic embedding recommender delivers nearly equivalent quality, especially in NDCG and HITS metrics showing its strength for capturing deeper contextual similarity. Maintaining both content-based pipelines in the backend enables flexible experimentation and easy integration of hybrid recommendation logic's, allowing the system to adapt as more user interaction data becomes available or as new tourism content is introduced. Storing the source type for each recommendation further supports A/B testing [8] and fine-grained control over which recommendations are shown for each user or activity.

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